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- 13.00.00 Pedagogika fanlari
- 13.00.01 Pedagogika nazariyasi. Pedagogik ta'limotlar tarixi
- 13.00.02 Ta'lim va tarbiya nazariyasi va metodikasi (sohalar bo'yicha)
- 13.00.03 Maxsus pedagogika
- 13.00.04 Jismoniy tarbiya va sport mashg'ulotlari nazariyasi va metodikasi
- 13.00.05 Kasb-hunar ta'limi nazariyasi va metodikasi
- 13.00.06 Elektron ta'lim nazariyasi va metodikasi (ta'lim sohaları va bosqichlari bo'yicha)
- 13.00.07 Ta'limda menejment
- 13.00.08 Maktabgacha ta'lim va tarbiya nazariyasi va metodikasi
- 13.00.09 Ijtimoiy pedagogika
- 07.00.00 Tarix fanlari
- 19.00.00 Psixologiya fanlari
- 01.00.00 Fizika-matematika fanlari
- 02.00.00 Kimyo fanlari
- 03.00.00 Biologiya fanlari
- 09.00.00 Falsafa fanlari
- 10.00.00 Filologiya fanlari
- 11.00.00 Geografiya fanlari

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SOFT TISSUE CONTROL: IN THE AESTHETIC ZONE

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Abstract: Preserving the natural appearance of the peri-implant area is one of the main challenges in implant-supported rehabilitation of the anterior region. A 48-year-old Saudi woman presented to the prosthodontic clinic complaining of the unaesthetic appearance of her maxillary anterior teeth. Clinical examination revealed advanced periodontitis affecting teeth [12,11,21,22]. After consultation with a periodontist, it was decided to extract these teeth and immediately place implants in the sockets of teeth [11,22] with the intention of immediate loading. Although implant placement was performed, adequate primary stability was not achieved. Therefore, the treatment plan was modified to include a transitional denture as a temporary restoration and the fabrication of customized healing abutments to preserve the soft tissue architecture. Three months later, gingivoplasty and a temporary restoration using the dynamic compression method were performed for soft tissue management. Subsequently, a modified impression coping was used to record the soft tissue contours and implant positions in the dental arch for fabrication of the definitive prosthesis. An indirect-direct technique was employed to transfer and replicate the cervical contours of the provisional restorations. This technique facilitates the creation of an optimal emergence profile by controlling the gingival contour around the implant-supported prosthesis. It is a relatively simple, accurate, and reliable method for precise replication of the soft tissue profile. By eliminating the intraoral use of resin monomer, the described approach reduces gingival stress and prevents thermal or chemical injury to the tissues. Additionally, by shaping the soft tissue during healing to achieve the desired contour, it minimizes the need for additional surgical intervention. Furthermore, a key advantage is the prevention of soft tissue collapse during the impression procedure, thereby ensuring accurate peri-implant soft tissue morphology. This case report describes the dynamic compression technique with provisional restorations in the aesthetic zone, as well as an alternative impression protocol that accurately records the peri-implant soft tissue contours and emergence profile following provisional restoration placement.

Key words: soft tissue management, implant, aesthetic zone.

Annotatsiya: Peri-implant sohaning tabiiy ko'inishini saqlash frontal sohada implantatsion reabilitatsiyani amalga oshirishda asosiy muammolardan biridir. 48 yoshli Saudiya Arabistoni fuqarosi yuqori frontal tishlarining estetik jihatdan qoniqarsiz ko'inishi sababli ortopedik stomatologiya klinikasiga murojaat qildi. Klinik tekshiruv natijasida [12,11,21,22] tishlarda og'ir darajadagi parodontit aniqlandi. Parodontolog bilan maslahatlashilgach, ushbu tishlarni olib tashlash va [11,22] tish kataklariga implantatlar o'rnatib, darhol yuklama berish rejalashtirildi. Biroq implantatsiya amalga oshirilganidan so'ng yetarli birlamchi barqarorlikka erishilmadi. Shu sababli davolash rejasi o'zgartirildi: vaqtinchalik olinadigan protez hamda yumshoq to'qimalar arxitekturasini saqlash uchun individual shakllantiruvchi abutmentlar tayyorlandi. Uch oy o'tgach, yumshoq to'qimalarni boshqarish maqsadida gingivoplastika va dinamik kompressiya usuli asosida vaqtinchalik protezlash bajarildi. Keyingi bosqichda dental yoyda implantatlar joylashuvi va yumshoq to'qimalar konturlarini aniq qayd etish hamda yakuniy ortopedik konstruksiyani tayyorlash uchun modifikatsiyalangan o'lchov transferi qo'llanildi. Vaqtinchalik restavratsiyalarning servikal konturlarini ko'chirish va takrorlash uchun bilvosita-to'g'ridan-to'g'ri usuldan foydalanildi. Ushbu texnika implant atrofidagi milk konturini nazorat qilish orqali optimal chiqish profilini shakllantirishga yordam beradi. Metod nisbatan soddah, aniq va ishonchli bo'lib, yumshoq to'qimalar profilini yuqori aniqlikda takrorlash imkonini beradi. Og'iz bo'shlig'ida smola monomeridan foydalanishni istisno etish milkka tushadigan yuklamani kamaytiradi hamda to'qimalarning termik yoki kimyoviy shikastlanishining oldini oladi. Shuningdek, bitish jarayonida yumshoq to'qimalarni zarur shaklga keltirish qo'shimcha jarrohlik aralashuviga bo'lgan ehtiyojni kamaytiradi. Muhim afzalliklardan biri – o'lchov olish jarayonida yumshoq to'qimalarning kollapsini oldini olish bo'lib, bu peri-implant konturlarni aniq aks ettirishni ta'minlaydi. Mazkur klinik holatda estetik zonada vaqtinchalik restavratsiyalar bilan dinamik kompressiya usuli hamda implant o'rnatilgandan keyingi chiqish profilini va peri-implant yumshoq to'qimalar konturlarini aniq qayd etishga imkon beruvchi muqobil o'lchov protokoli tavsiflangan.

Kalit so'zlar: yumshoq to'qimalarni boshqarish, implantat, estetik zona.

Аннотация: Сохранение естественного вида периимплантатной области является одной из основных задач при имплантологической реабилитации во фронтальном отделе. В клинику ортопедической стоматологии обратилась 48-летняя жительница Саудовской Аравии с жалобами на неэстетичный вид верхних фронтальных зубов. При клиническом обследовании выявлен выраженный пародонтит зубов [12,11,21,22]. После консультации с пародонтологом было принято решение об удалении данных зубов и немедленной установке имплантатов в лунки зубов [11,22] с планируемой немедленной нагрузкой. Однако после установки имплантатов достаточная первичная стабильность достигнута не была. В связи с этим план лечения был изменён: изготовлен временный съёмный протез и индивидуальные формирователи десны для сохранения архитектуры мягких тканей. Через три месяца были выполнены гингивопластика и временное протезирование с применением метода динамической компрессии для коррекции мягких тканей. Далее использовался модифицированный трансфер для снятия оттиска с целью точной регистрации контуров мягких тканей и положения имплантатов в зубной дуге для изготовления окончательной ортопедической конструкции. Применялась непрямо-прямая техника для переноса и воспроизведения пришеечных контуров временных реставраций. Данная методика способствует формированию оптимального профиля выхода за счёт контроля десневого контура вокруг имплантологической конструкции. Метод является относительно простым, точным и надёжным способом воспроизведения профиля мягких тканей. Исключение внутриорального применения мономера смолы снижает нагрузку на десну и предотвращает термическое или химическое повреждение тканей. Кроме того, формирование мягких тканей в процессе заживления до требуемой формы уменьшает необходимость дополнительного хирургического вмешательства. Существенным преимуществом является предотвращение коллапса мягких тканей во время снятия оттиска, что обеспечивает точную передачу периимплантатных контуров. В представленном клиническом случае описан метод динамической компрессии с использованием временных реставраций в эстетической зоне, а также альтернативный протокол снятия оттиска, обеспечивающий точную регистрацию контуров мягких тканей и профиля выхода после установки временной конструкции.

Ключевые слова: управление мягкими тканями, имплантат, эстетическая зона.

INTRODUCTION

Achieving long-term and stable outcomes in implant treatment, particularly in the anterior aesthetic zone of the jaw, has been the primary focus of contemporary dental research [1-3].

The loss of more than 50% of bone mass and significant negative changes in soft tissue quality and volume are characteristic of bone remodeling that develops rapidly during the first three to six months after extraction. As “tension syndrome” develops, the height of the interdental papillae decreases, and the gingival contour, biotype, and morphology of the edentulous crest change. This worsens the clinical condition, particularly in the aesthetic segment of the jaw [4-6].

These modifications require a multi-phase preparation process for implant placement (bone and soft tissue augmentation), which prolongs the recovery period and often yields unsatisfactory results [7,8].

LITERATURE REVIEW

Most clinicians now prefer immediate implantation, which involves placing a dental implant directly into the extraction socket [9-11]. The anterior jaw segment, which is visible during smiling, particularly benefits from this treatment approach, as it preserves bone volume, supports soft tissues, and shortens treatment time [12]. The appearance of the gingiva and overall dental health are essential for an attractive natural smile. However, the morphological structure of the alveolar bone processes and jaw segments often limits the application of immediate implantation in the anterior region. In 75% of cases, the facial wall is thin, with a thickness of less than 1 mm, and in nearly 100% of cases, it undergoes resorption after tooth extraction [13]. The inner portion of the alveolar socket wall, known as the “bundle bone,” is a tooth-dependent structure that rapidly resorbs after extraction, resulting in horizontal and subsequently vertical bone deficiencies, as well as alterations in the gingival contour within a short period of time [14].

Pathological events such as inflammation and stress caused by endodontic tooth preparation for prosthetic restoration may also lead to defects of the anterior alveolar bone wall [15]. Some authors argue that dental implantation should not be performed under these circumstances because it reduces implant longevity and produces inferior aesthetic outcomes, particularly when the gingival biotype is thin [16,17]. This underscores the importance of developing novel techniques for immediate implantation in complex clinical scenarios within the aesthetic zone of the jaw. The objective of this study was to develop a procedure for immediate implantation in the anterior maxilla with bone deficiency and to assess its effectiveness.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Our research was conducted at the clinics of the Department of Surgical Dentistry and Maxillofacial Surgery of Samarkand State Medical University. Seventy-five patients underwent surgery, including 30 men and 45 women. Each patient provided written informed consent in accordance with the 2013 Helsinki Declaration. The study was carried out after obtaining approval from the Ethics Committee of Samarkand State Medical University.

Clinical analysis: Prior to surgery, each patient was evaluated using aesthetic charts developed on the basis of the modified Pink Aesthetic Score proposed by Fürhauser et al. [18]. The most significant soft tissue aesthetic parameters included in the charts were the height of the distal and mesial interdental papillae, the width of the keratinized gingival zone, the gingival zenith, and the thickness of the alveolar ridge relative to the corresponding tooth area on the contralateral side. **X-ray analysis:** Cone-beam computed tomography (CBCT) was used to assess alveolar ridge height and thickness, as well as the thickness of the facial alveolar bone wall at points A1, A2, and A3, measured in millimeters for each patient. Additionally, the Hounsfield unit (HU) scale was used to determine soft tissue indices (gingival radiodensity) in the intervention area.

All these indicators were reassessed four months, six months, and one year after surgery. Since gingival recessions accompanied by aesthetic complications are often observed in the implant area during the one-year postoperative period, the indicators obtained at this time were considered particularly significant. **The immediate implantation technique:** We developed and patented a novel technique for immediate dental implantation [19]. By incorporating a xenogenic collagen matrix and a collagen membrane, the proposed method stabilizes the facial alveolar bone while preserving and shaping the contours of the alveolar ridge. The denser distribution of collagen fibers in the epithelial margin and the de-epithelialized zone of mixed connective tissue grafts, which we use to prevent recurrent recessions in the implant area over time, reinforces and stabilizes the marginal gingiva. The area of loose connective tissue covering the entire surface of the middle and apical thirds of the facial bone wall increases the volume of tissues protecting the xenogenic graft and the surrounding bone mass [20,21].

According to the classification proposed by Elian et al. [22], patients were divided into three groups based on the surgical treatment protocol in the maxillary aesthetic zone to evaluate the effectiveness of the proposed method. Patients diagnosed with "chronic apical periodontitis" and "tooth root fracture" were assigned to Groups 1 and 2, whereas patients diagnosed with "partial anterior adentia" were assigned to Group 3. In Group 1 (n = 25), patients presented with a medium or thick gingival biotype, and the thickness of the intact facial bone wall was 1 mm or greater. The treatment plan included immediate implantation performed according to the standard protocol [23].

Patients in Group 2 (n = 20) exhibited a thin gingival biotype and were diagnosed with defects in the coronal third of the facial alveolar bone wall (≤ 5 mm) or a wall thickness of < 1 mm. Twelve patients in this group (Group 2a) underwent immediate implantation combined with soft tissue plastic repair using free connective tissue grafts. This type of graft was selected due to its high biological potential for soft tissue regeneration [24].

Although it provides an opportunity to increase tissue thickness, its flexibility does not always allow for modification of gingival morphology or enhancement of gingival density in the implant neck region, which is critical for preventing gingival recession. Therefore, the proposed immediate implantation procedure was performed in the remaining patients of Group 2 (Group 2b). This technique differs in that it employs a mixed autograft comprising the epithelial margin, the de-epithelialized zone, and connective tissue. Owing to the denser arrangement of collagen fibers in such grafts, increased gingival density allows stabilization of the gingival margin, the surrounding xenogenic material, and the anterior alveolar wall.

Immediate placement of the dental implant into the extraction socket, preservation of the interdental papillae and the gingival contour zenith, modification of the soft tissue biotype, and reconstruction of the facial bone wall enabled reduction of treatment time, improvement of clinical predictability, and achievement of favorable aesthetic outcomes in implant therapy. Patients in Group 3 (n = 25) presented with soft tissue and bone deficiencies in the anterior maxilla following tooth extraction, which precluded immediate dental implant placement. These patients underwent staged delayed implantation with soft tissue augmentation and bone grafting procedures [25].

Data processing: The acquired data were analyzed using the Statistica 6.0 software package (StatSoft Inc., USA) and standard statistical methods. Calculations were performed using absolute values (mm) and percentages (%) to evaluate the effectiveness of the proposed treatment approach. Fisher's exact test and Student's t-test were applied to assess the reliability of the findings in small sample groups. Differences were considered statistically significant at $p \leq 0.05$, at $p \leq 0.05$, the differences were considered statistically significant.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

The study findings indicate that the proposed rapid implantation technique is effective in achieving a stable gingival contour while preserving alveolar ridge volume in the dental implant region of the smile zone. A comparison of groups 2a and 2b, in which mixed and connective tissue grafts were used, with group 1, in which rapid implantation was performed according to the conventional technique, demonstrated significant improvements in “pink aesthetics” (Figure 4). When a connective tissue graft was applied, the gingival zeniths of the treated tooth and the corresponding contralateral tooth were reduced by 76% and 92%, respectively (Figure 5). The width of the keratinized attached gingiva is one of the most important prognostic factors for long-term implant survival. This zone forms a stable barrier that prevents microbial invasion of the underlying bone and subsequent resorption [26]. In our study, this parameter remained stable in groups 1 and 2; in fact, it did not change compared to preoperative values and was comparable to the same parameter of the contralateral tooth.

This once again demonstrates that soft tissue architecture can be preserved with rapid implantation and that interdental papillae can be maintained through the use of soft tissue grafts, thereby preventing the formation of black triangles and ensuring highly satisfactory aesthetic outcomes [27-29].

The findings of studies [4-6] are supported by the observation that in groups 1 and 2, the thickness of the facial bone wall decreased by more than 50% compared to preoperative values. According to the conventional technique, rapid implantation resulted in a statistically significant reduction in alveolar ridge thickness by 58-66% ($p \leq 0.05$), which was associated with partial resorption of the facial bone wall. One year after surgery, the difference in gingival zenith in group 1 increased by 163%, indicating the absence of favourable aesthetic effects and overall less favourable treatment outcomes.

CONCLUSION

In partially edentulous patients, the newly established technique of rapid implantation in bone-deficient conditions provides stable rehabilitation and consistently favorable aesthetic outcomes of implant therapy. The long-term results of this method are particularly effective when applied to complex dentoalveolar morphology, such as a thin facial alveolar bone wall (1 mm or less), its defects, and a thin gingival biotype. A clear advantage of the proposed approach is that, compared to conventional two-stage implant therapy protocols, patients' recovery times are nearly halved.

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- 13.00.00 Pedagogika fanlari
 - 13.00.01 Pedagogika nazariyasi. Pedagogik ta'limotlar tarixi
 - 13.00.02 Ta'lim va tarbiya nazariyasi va metodikasi (sohalar bo'yicha)
 - 13.00.03 Maxsus pedagogika
 - 13.00.04 Jismoniy tarbiya va sport mashg'ulotlari nazariyasi va metodikasi
 - 13.00.05 Kasb-hunar ta'limi nazariyasi va metodikasi
 - 13.00.06 Elektron ta'lim nazariyasi va metodikasi (ta'lim sohaları va bosqichlari bo'yicha)
 - 13.00.07 Ta'limda menejment
 - 13.00.08 Maktabgacha ta'lim va tarbiya nazariyasi va metodikasi
 - 13.00.09 Ijtimoiy pedagogika
 - 07.00.00 Tarix fanlari
 - 19.00.00 Psixologiya fanlari
 - 01.00.00 Fizika-matematika fanlari
 - 02.00.00 Kimyo fanlari
 - 03.00.00 Biologiya fanlari
 - 09.00.00 Falsafa fanlari
 - 10.00.00 Filologiya fanlari
 - 11.00.00 Geografiya fanlari

MAKTABGACHA VA MAKTAB TA'LIMI

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